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**ETHICS OF CARE AND FEMINIST ETHICS IN THE
CONTEXT OF PROTECTION OF CHILDREN BORN AS A
RESULT OF SEXUAL VIOLENCE IN CONFLICT**

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Kateryna Slinko. Ethics of Care and Feminist ethics in the context of Protection of children born as a result of sexual violence in conflict. This thesis explores the role of ethics of care and feminist ethics in the context of protecting children born of rape during armed conflict (CBOWR). These children, born as a result of sexual violence in conflict zones, are often neglected in legal and social discourses. Their status is frequently viewed within the broader context of conflict-related sexual violence, yet their unique needs remain largely unaddressed. The thesis examines the complexities surrounding the protection, rehabilitation, and social integration of these children, particularly in post-conflict societies where they face stigma, discrimination, and re-traumatization. Ethics of care, focused on nurturing the most vulnerable individuals, emphasizes the importance of providing safety, health, and psychological support. Feminist ethics critiques the structural inequalities and power dynamics that enable sexual violence, underscoring the need for systemic changes to support the rights of these children and their mothers. The paper advocates for a comprehensive strategy involving government, NGOs, and civil society to protect and support CBOWR through legal protection, social programs, and rehabilitation efforts. By applying both care ethics and feminist ethics, this approach seeks to ensure these children's dignity, well-being, and integration into society.

Keywords: *ethics of care, feminist ethics, sexual violence, children born of rape, conflict, legal protection, psychosocial rehabilitation, trauma.*

Survivors of conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV) are those who have been individually or collectively subjected to such violence, including children born as a result of rape. Currently, this category of children is primarily neglected in Ukrainian legal discourse. The status of these children is mostly considered in the context of CRCV.

Children born as a result of sexual violence during the war (children born of war rape, CBOWR) are a separate category of children whose existence is inextricably linked to the consequences of armed conflict. Their lives and personalities are shaped by violence, which makes them extremely vulnerable and requires a comprehensive approach to their protection and integration into society. Given the tragic nature of the situation, it is important to find ways to rehabilitate and integrate such children into traumatized, sometimes retraumatized families and communities, where they may face challenges due to a lack of acceptance and stigmatization of their origin. In this context, attention should be paid to the historical experience of transitional justice in South America and Africa, the international tribunals for Rwanda and the former Yugoslavia, as well as the practice of the International Criminal Court (ICC). An analysis of the social and legal consequences for children born as a result of sexual violence during conflict allows us to identify the specific problems faced by these children in war and post-war society, including in Ukraine. Considering these problems makes it possible to develop strategies to avoid and mitigate the negative consequences for these children.

The ethics of care (EoC) and feminist ethics play an important role in addressing this issue, aiming not only to support but also to rehabilitate child survivors of violence. The ethics of care, which is based on care, attention, and support for the most vulnerable people, including children, is focused on ensuring their safety, health, and well-being. It prioritizes humanitarian assistance, including psychosocial support, trauma treatment, and the provision of necessary resources for recovery. This approach emphasizes the need to protect children born as a result of sexual violence, not only in terms of physical well-being but also psychological recovery, which is critical in the process of adapting to normal life.

Feminist ethics analyses the power, social roles, and inequalities that contribute to violence, including sexual violence in war. It criticizes patriarchal structures that lead to the stigmatization of children born of violence. Along with the ethics of care, it emphasizes the importance of legal and social protection, psychosocial support, and the fight against discrimination, contributing to changing social norms and overcoming inequality.

The goal of feminist ethics is to transform societies and situations where women are harmed through violence, subordination, and exclusion. When such injustices are evident now and in the future, radical feminist activists will continue their work of protest and action after careful assessment and reflection (McLellan, 2010, p. 240)

With violence, we are once again returning to masculine behavior and the traditional ethics that encouraged such behavior and attitudes. In modern society, in the twentieth century, violence against women is becoming less and less socially acceptable (Mohrmann, 2015, pp. 185—192.)

Alison Watson discusses the issue of children born as a result of wartime rape and uses feminist ethical theory to address these marginalized issues. Invisibility is emphasized in the traditional construction of much of the existing international discourse on motherhood as an ‘activity in the private sphere’, where important issues such as children raped during the war can be lost in the translation of international dialogue and minimally affected (Watson, 2007). Feminist ethical theory is presented in terms of expanding theoretical dialogues about international relations and addressing marginalized issues.

Puechguirbal argues that conflict is a ‘gendered experience’ and discusses the importance of peacekeeping operations that monitor the differential impact of war on women, men, boys, and girls in post-conflict societies so as not to marginalize the most vulnerable groups (Puechguirbal, 2009, p. 171). Applying feminist ethics in peacebuilding and reconstruction strategies could cover a broader range of issues and is not considered a pressing issue in international relations dialogues. Current strategies are not achieving their goals of establishing peace and ending gender-based violence and

sexual abuse, which continue to be at high levels. This remains a legacy of post-conflict societies that needs to be addressed. The introduction of feminist ethics contributes to creating more gender-responsive peacekeeping and peacebuilding strategies that meet the needs of both sexes and are implemented in institutions and society. (Puechguirbal, 2009).

The thesis emphasizes the need for a comprehensive strategy to ensure the protection of the rights of children born as a result of conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV). This strategy should include active cooperation between government agencies, NGOs, and civil society representatives, as addressing the issue of these children requires a multifaceted approach and coordination at all levels. This is the only way to ensure that these children are properly supported and integrated into society and that they and their mothers are afforded legal protection.

Determining the status of CBOWR at the national level is key to their social adaptation and rehabilitation. It is important to provide comprehensive support, including education, psychological assistance, and social integration. Data collection on CBOWR should be sensitive and focused on practical protection. Taking into account the needs of children and mothers who have experienced violence will help to create an effective support system and contribute to their recovery.

Thus, creating a comprehensive strategy for the protection of CBOWR is not only a matter of legal and social justice but also a key element on the way to ensuring a decent life for these children and their mothers in post-war Ukrainian society.

Conclusions:

The problems of children born as a result of sexual violence during the war are currently invisible to Ukrainian society, and it will take years to fully experience and understand how this will affect the lives of CBOWR, their mothers, and their communities. Already, we must prevent the potential marginalization and rejection of these children by society.

A feminist ethic is essential to addressing the issues of children born as a result of conflict-related sexual violence. It helps to view the situation through the lens of gender inequality, marginalization, and the consequences of structures of violence in patriarchal

systems. The sexual violence that leads to the birth of such children reflects a broader context where women and children are vulnerable and their rights are violated.

Feminist ethics emphasizes the need to change social stereotypes and combat the stigma that accompanies CBOWR. It also emphasizes the importance of protecting the rights of the mothers of these children, who often face trauma and isolation. The development of a strategy to support CBOWR should take into account not only legal mechanisms but also social programs to avoid marginalizing these individuals.

In general, feminist ethics calls for the creation of a just environment where children and their mothers can receive the necessary support and protection to facilitate their recovery and integration into society.

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